

Frequency-Domain 2×2 MIMO Equalizer with Stokes Space Updating Algorithm

F. J. Vaquero Caballero^{1,2}, A. Zanaty^{1,3}, F. Pittalà¹, G. Goeger¹, Y. Ye¹, I. Tafur Monroy², W. Rosenkranz³

1: European Research Center, Huawei Technologies Duesseldorf GmbH, Riesstrasse 25, D-80992 Munich, Germany, fabio.pittala@huawei.com,

2: Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Department of Photonics Engineering, Ørsted Plads, Build. 343, DK-2800.

3: Chair for Communications, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Kaiserstraße 2, D-24143 Kiel, Germany,

Abstract: We propose a novel frequency-domain Stokes space algorithm. Its low implementation complexity architecture allows merging static and dynamic 2×2 MIMO equalization in a single stage.

OCIS codes: (060.1660) Coherent communications; (060.2330) Fiber optics communications.

1. Introduction

Coherent receivers employing digital signal processing are capable of efficiently compensating linear signal impairments. A typical equalization implementation compensates the static impairments, such as chromatic dispersion (CD), by using long frequency-domain (FD) FIR filters, while dynamic effects, such as polarization-mode dispersion (PMD), by using adaptive butterfly time-domain (TD) FIR filters [1]. The 2×2 multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) equalizer can totally rely on training-sequences [2] or can be updated with algorithms like the constant-modulus algorithm (CMA) or the least-mean-square (LMS) algorithm which make use also of the payload data. Dynamic equalizers are also capable of compensating filtering effects and residual CD [1]. Recently, a 2×2 MIMO equalization approach named Stokes space algorithm (SSA) was presented [3]. It provides a faster convergence speed, stronger robustness against carrier phase noise and frequency offset than CMA [3].

In this paper, we propose a FD implementation of the SSA, which allows merging static and dynamic equalization having no penalty compared to FD LMS implementation.

2. The SSA algorithm

The standard structure of the 2×2 MIMO TD equalizer [3], is composed of 4 filters: $\mathbf{h}_{xx}^{(n)}$, $\mathbf{h}_{xy}^{(n)}$, $\mathbf{h}_{yx}^{(n)}$ and $\mathbf{h}_{yy}^{(n)}$. The equalized signals x_o and y_o are obtained as:

$$x_o(n) = \mathbf{x}_i^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{xx}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}_i^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{xy}^{(n)}, y_o(n) = \mathbf{x}_i^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{yx}^{(n)} + \mathbf{y}_i^{(n)} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{yy}^{(n)} \quad (1)$$

The signals after equalization are transformed into the Stokes space to calculate the new error. The transformation into the Stokes space is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= |x_o(n)|^2 - |y_o(n)|^2 \\ S_2 &= 2\Re\{x_o(n)y_o^*(n)\} \\ S_3 &= 2\Im\{x_o(n)y_o^*(n)\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi_d = \varphi_x - \varphi_y$. The filter coefficients are updated in each iteration using the stochastic gradient descent approach [1]. The update rules and the gradients calculations are functions of the coefficients $C_1(n)$ and $C_2(n)$ [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n+1)} &= \mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)} - \mu \nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}); l, m \in \{x, y\} \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{h}_{lm}^{(n)}} f(\mathbf{h}^{(n)}) &= C_p(n) \cdot (\mathbf{z}_i^{(n)})^* \\ p &= \begin{cases} 1, & l = x \\ 2, & l = y' \end{cases} \quad z = \begin{cases} x, & m = x \\ y, & m = y \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The calculation of $C_1(n)$ and $C_2(n)$ is shown in Fig. 1. Since the equalization to obtain x_o and y_o is a convolution in TD, it can be transformed into a multiplication in FD [4]. The weight update of the filter coefficients is performed every $N/2$ symbols instead of every symbol, being N the block length, leading to a slower convergence.

3. System overview of the frequency implementation

The 2×2 MIMO FD equalizer with updating according to SSA is shown in Fig. 1. It is based on a FD LMS implementation [4]. The proposed implementation employs blocks of N symbols using 2 samples per symbol. The colored blocks represent functions that involve both polarization components (\mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{y}_i) while the colorless blocks work independently for each polarization. Equalization in FD is performed by the 50% overlap-save technique [4].

The algorithm starts by concatenating two blocks and doing the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the $2N$ signal. Afterwards the signal is equalized in the FD, by sample-wise multiplication. After equalization the signal is converted into TD obtained by an inverse FFT (IFFT). The second half of the block contains the equalized signal (x_o and y_o) while the first half is discarded. Based on the equalized signals, the error is calculated for both LMS and SSA. SSA algorithms involve the conversion into Stokes domain and the calculation of C_1 and C_2 , which are the coefficients multiplying the weights update in SSA. For clarity, Fig. 1 includes the calculation of the SSA error.

Once the error is calculated, the signals are zero padded corresponding to the region of the previous block and converted into FD. The multiplication block, 'X', executes the gradient calculation involving the conjugated signals and the respective errors for SSA in the FD, resulting in the gradient updates shown in (3). After that an optional block involving a constraint is applied. In our setup, this operation limits the response of the filters to a length of N taps accelerating the convergence speed [4]. Finally the weight update is accomplished in the FD.

Fig. 1: 2x2 MIMO FD equalizer with tap weight update based on the SSA.

4. Performance analysis

Performance evaluation is based on a 32Gbaud non-return-to-zero (NRZ) dual-polarization QPSK system. The transmission system employed for performance evaluation, fully emulates the generation of the signal from the electrical to the optical layer including filters. The FFT used for the FD equalizer has 64 points, which corresponds to a 32-tap window for input signals of two samples per symbol

The performance of both algorithms is analyzed under different random state-of-polarization (SOP) rotation for all the simulation cases. Simulations are performed for multiple cases and results are averaged. The step size was optimized for the back-to-back case for each algorithm independently. The step size employed was $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $1.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ for LMS and SSA respectively. The OSNR versus BER for both algorithms is shown in Fig. 2a). We observe same performance for LMS and SSA FD implementations. We also show the behavior of FD LMS and FD SSA in presence of polarization dependent loss (PDL) and CD (Fig 2b and c). In the case of SSA implementation in the FD, we tested the performance for different laser linewidth obtaining the same performance as the case of the TD [3].

Fig. 2a): BER versus OSNR curve for TD LMS and TD SSA.

Fig. 2b): PDL tolerance (BER=10⁻³), for FD equalization.

Fig. 2c): OSNR penalty as a function of CD (BER=10⁻³).

Fig. 2d): TD and FD computational complexity of LMS and SSA.

Fig. 2d) shows a complexity analysis for different equalizers. The metric used is complex multiplications per symbol. The complexity of TD LMS is: $4N + 2$ [5] and the TD SSA complexity is: $4N + 8$. For the case of the FD implementations, we rely on our own analysis, note that we aim to provide the reader with an intuition of the complexity, a detailed study is needed to explore different optimization possibilities. We assume that FFTs of N points have $N/2 \log_2 N$ complex multiplications [5]. The total complexity of our implementation is: $20 \log_2(2N) + 24$ and $20 \log_2(2N) + 30$ for FD LMS and FD SSA, respectively. Doubling the number of taps from 32 to 64 only increments the complexity by 15% for the FD implementations while TD algorithm complexity is doubled.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced the FD implementation of the SSA algorithm, having the same performance than FD LMS in terms of BER versus OSNR. FD implementations are suitable for low complexity implementations, in our case only increasing by 15% when the number of taps is doubled. The small increment of the complexity with the number of taps allows merging the static and the dynamic equalization. Further study of the convergence speed of FD SSA is under investigation, but literature has already shown its benefits in convergence speed for the TD implementation.

This work has been supported by the EC through H2020 project ROAM (grant no: 645361, www.roam-project.eu).

6. References

- [1] S. J. Savory, "Digital filters for coherent optical receivers," *Opt. Exp.* **16** (2), 804-817 (2008).
- [2] F. Pittalà et al., "Training-Aided Frequency-Domain Channel Estimation and Equalization for Single-Carrier Coherent Optical Transmission Systems," in *J. Lightwave Technol.* **32** (24), 4849-4863 (2014).
- [3] M. Visintin et al., "Adaptive Digital Equalization in Optical Coherent Receivers with Stokes-Space Update Algorithm," *J. Lightwave Technol.* **32** (24), 4759-4767 (2014).
- [4] J. J. Shynk, "Frequency-domain and multirate adaptive filtering," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* **9** (1), 14-37 (1992).
- [5] N. Benvenuto and G. Cherubini, *Algorithms for Communications Systems and Their Applications*, Chichester, U.K., Wiley (2002).